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Socio Economic Status of Sugarcane Farmers: A Case Study of Hapur District Uttar Pradesh

Rajeev Kumar *

Sugarcane is a most important crop for sugar production in the world and main cash crop of India also. It is a key factor in the upliftment of socio-economic condition of sugarcane farmers. It is one of the most significant kharif crop of Uttar Pradesh economy. Sugarcane occupations nearly 70% of cultivated land in western U.P. the study is leased on primary data and conducted in 2016. To study the socio-economic status of sugarcane farmers, a sample of 160 respondent was taken out randomly from five village of District Hapur, which is situated in western Uttar Pradesh. The maximum sugarcane farmers belonged to backward

Keywords:- Sugarcane, Sugarcane farmers, socio-economic,

Introduction:- sugarcane is an important commercial crop of the world sugarcane is several & pieces, native to the warm temperate to tropical reigns of South East Asia, Brazil and America like Caribbean Island. Brazil is the large Producer of sugarcane in the world. The next five major producers in decreasing amount of production are India, China, Thailand, Pakistan and Mexico. It is a crop of multiple use for producing Sugar ethanol and fiber etc. Sugarcane is one of the important commercial crops in grown India occupying around 3.8 hectare of land with an annual can production of around 270 millions tones. Sugarcane industry is second largest agro based industry after textile in India. Major sugarcane producing state are Maharashtra, Tamilnadu, Karnataka, U.P. ,Andhra Pradesh, Bihar, Gujarat, Haryana, Punjab, and Uttarakhand, A many all states in the country. Sugarcane prices are better than that of many other crop will also attract farmers to this tropical crop. Sugarcane gives almost double the returns compeered to most other crops (Ram antham, 2013).

In India, Uttar Pradesh alone accounts for 42.47% of total area and 41.31% of total production of sugarcane. The sugarcane cultivation and sugar industry are the main source of socio-economic development in the rural areas mobilizing rural resources and generating higher income and employment opportunities in Uttar Pradesh. The average production of Uttar Pradesh is 60.96 tons/hac. Which is lower than other state like Tamilnadu, Karnataka, Maharashtra (tropical) and Punjab (subtropical). Thus it is urgently needed to increase the productivity of sugarcane for required level of supply to the factory one hand and prove its worth when compared with prevailing crop in the area on the other land (Arun kumar-2017)

The study area: Hapur District is a District of Uttar Pradesh state of India. Panchsheel Nagar was created from the tehsil of Hapur, Garhmukteshwer, and Dholana, previously of Ghaziabad District as one of three new district of Uttar Pradesh in september 2011. District Hapur was renamed from Panchsheel Nagar to Hapur on 23 July 2012. District is a part of Meerut Division. It is located between 28*43 to 77*46 north latitude. Hapur district surrounded on the west by district Ghaziabad, north by the Meerut south by Bulandshahar and east by the J.P.Nagar, district. The district is situated almost in a flat area with gentles and this district are sugarcane, wheat and rice etc. It is a prominent agriculture district.

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Objectives : The paper is written with the objectives.

- 1- To study socio-economic condition of sugarcane farmers.
- 2- To study sugarcane farmers finance and cropping status of sugarcane.

Methodology : This study is based on primary data for the period of year (2016-17). Sugarcane farmers belongs to different size of land holding like marginal (73), small(57), and medium(30), have been selected randomly from the village namely Niyajpur Khaiyya , Khudiliya, Bihuani, Bharana and Bdarkha, For the purpose of the study ten variables age education caste occupation family size family type land holding annual income source of irrigation taken into consideration which constituted the socio-economic profile of sugarcane farmers, simple statistical tools like percentage was used for analyses and interpretation of data.

Result and discussion:- socio-economic profile of sugarcane farmers.

Age of sugarcane growers:- The age structure of a population refers to the numbers of people in different age group (www.yourarticlelibrary.com/population). It is evident from table-1 that majority 42.46% marginal growers belonged to 40 above age group. 16.43%, 16.43% and 24.65% marginal belonged to below 30 age group, 30-35 age group and 35-40 age group respectively.

In case of small farmers maximum 40.35% small farmers belonged to 40 above age group, while minimum (12.28%) small farmers belonged to 35-40 age group. Remaining 13.33% , 26.66% and 10% medium farmers belonged to below 30 age group , 30-35 age group and 40 above age group respectively,

It is clear from table 1 that most of the sugarcane farmers belonged to 35-45 age group and 40 above age group It can be said that going farmers are very interested to grow sugarcane.

Table-1 Age composition of farmers (in percent)

S.No	Age categories	Marginal farmers (N=73)	Small farmers (N=57)	Medium farmers (N=30)	Total (N=160)
1	Below-30	16.43%	12.28%	13.34%	14.37
2	30-35	16.43%	17.54%	26.66%	18.75
3	35-40	24.65%	29.82%	50.00%	31.25
4	40 above	42.46%	40.35%	10.00%	35.62

Source-Field survey 2016-2017.

Education level of sugarcane farmers: Education is one of the most important asset for an individual as it provide the key to the understanding of the society and equal the individual to assert his rights and claim due share from others. Education not only improve level of awareness and knowledge but also changes attitude and rules, moderns and socio economic benefit and social prestige are derived from formal education, A place of respectability is given to education (kendre, 2011)

It is evident from table -2 that 27.39% marginal farmers were having education up to high school followed by 20.54 % ,16.43% , 12.32 % and 12.32% marginal farmers were having up to junior high school, up to primary, up to intermediate and graduation, respectively. Only 10.95 % marginal farmers were found illiterate.

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Table-2:- Education level of farmers (%)

S.No	Education level	Marginal farmers(N=73)	Small farmers (N=57)	Medium farmers(N=30)	Total (N=160)
1	Illiterate	10.95	3.50	3.33	6.87
2	Up to primary	16.43	19.29	16.66	17.50
3	Up to junior HS	20.54	17.54	16.66	18.75
4	Up to High school	27.39	31.57	30.00	29.37
5	Intermediate	12.32	17.54	23.33	16.25
6	Graduate	12.32	10.52	10.00	11.25

Source-Field survey 2016-17.

In the case of small farmers 31.57% were having up to High school level of education followed by 19.29%, 17.54%, 17.54%, 10.52% small farmers having up to primary, up to junior high school, intermediate, and graduate level of education, respectively. Only 3.50% small farmers were found illiterate. In the case of medium sugarcane growers 30% were educated up to high school level, while 3.33% of the medium farmers were found illiterate.

Thus, it is clear from table-2 that maximum respondents were having up to high school. Only some sugarcane farmers were found illiterate. It means most of educated persons were having interest of sugarcane cultivation.

Caste composition: The caste system in India is the paradigmatic ethnographic example of caste. It has origins in ancient India and was transformed by various ruling elites in medieval, early modern and modern India, especially the mughal empire and the British Raj. It is today the basic of educational and job reservation India-(<https://en.m.wikipedia.org/caste>)

It is evident from table-3 that 47.94% marginal farmers belonged to backward caste and 28.23% belonged to general caste and 23.28% belonged to scheduled caste. In case of medium farmers maximum 52.63% were belonged to backward caste followed by 28.07% belonged to general caste and 19.29% belonged to scheduled caste. In case of medium farmers maximum 53.33% belonged to backward caste followed by 40.00% general caste and 10.00% belonged scheduled caste, respective.

Thus it is clear from table-3, that must of sugarcane growers belonged to backward caste. It means backward people were using sugarcane as a cash crop, which will be helpful for upliftment of socio-economic status of sugarcane growers.

Table-3

S.N.	Caste category	Marginal farmers(N=73)	Small farmers(N=57)	Medium farmers(N=30)	Total=160
1	SC	28.76	19.29	10.00	21.87
2	OBC	47.94	52.63	53.33	50.62
3	GEN.	23.28	28.07	40.00	28.12

Source : Field survey 2016-17

Occupation of sugarcane growers: In every household some of the members are involved full time in agriculture where as there others expense part time by practicing subsidiary and casual occupations

Table-4 shown that majority of the marginal growers 50%, small 28% , and medium farmers 40% were adopting agriculture as a main occupation 24.65%, adopting agriculture with business. Rest percent were adopting Agriculture+ Business+ service.

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Table -4 : Occupation of the sugarcane growers (%)

S.N.	Occupation level	Marginal (N=73)	Small Farmers (N=57)	Medium Farmers(N=30)	Total=160
1	Agriculture	68.49	49.12	66.66	61.25
2	Agri.+Business	24.65	42.10	26.66	31.25
3	Agri+Bus.+Ser.	6.84	8.77	6.66	7.50

Source: field survey 2016-17

Family type : It is evident from table-5 that maximum 57.53% , marginal farmers were belonged to joint family and 42.46% were belonged to nuclear family system. in the case of small farmers 64.91% were belonged to joint family and 35.08% farmers belonged to nuclear system. Similary 63.79% medium farmers belonged to joint family.

Table-5 : Family type of sugarcane growers(%)

S.N.	Family type	Marginal farmers(N=73)	Small farmers(N=57)	Medium farmers(N=30)	Total=160
1	Nuclear	42.46	35.08	36.66	38.75
2	Joint	57.53	64.91	63.79	61.25

Source:- field survey 2016-17

Table-6 : Family size of sugarcane growers(%)

S.N.	Family size	Marginal farmers(N=73)	Small farmers(N=57)	Medium farmers(N=30)	Total=160
1	Small	28.76	19.29	26.00	25.00
2	Medium	61.64	64.91	60.00	62.50
3	Large	9.58	15.78	13.33	12.50

Source: field survey 2016-17

Land holding : It is the evident from table-7, that 45.62 %respondents had marginal size of land holding. While 35.62% respondents had small size of holding and only 18.75% respondents had medium size of land holding. It is clear that the majority of the sugarcane farmers belonged to marginal farmers category

Table-7 : Distribution of sugarcane growers a per size of land holding (N=160)

S.N.	Land holding	Respondents	Percent
1	Marginal farmers (up to 1hac.)	73	45.62%
2	Small farmers (1to 2hac)	57	35.62%
3	Medium farmers (2 to 4 hac.	30	18.75%

Source: field survey 2016-17

Annual Income of sugarcane growers : It is the evident from table-8 that maximum 42.46% marginal farmers belonged to lower income group followed by 40.00% and 18.00% marginal farmers belonged to medium and higher income group, respectively. In case of small farmers 74% farmers belonged to medium income group followed by 18% and 8% belonged to high income and low income groups, respectively. In case of medium farmers majority 67%

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belonged medium income group followed by 23% and 10% belonged to high and low income groups, respectively.

Thus, It is clear from table-8 that the majority of sugarcane growers belonged to medium income group.

Table-8 : Annual income of sugarcane growers (%)

S.No.	Annual income	Marginal farmers (N=73)	Small farmers (N=57)	Medium farmers (N=30)	Total (N=160)
1	Lower income (20,000)	42.46	08.00	10.00	24.00
2	Medium income (20-40 ths.)	40.00	74.00	67.00	62.00
3	High income 50,000 above	18.00	18.00	23.00	19.00

Source: field survey 2016-17

Source of Irrigation : In case of marginal farmers 45% were using canal+ private tubwell / pumpset as a source of irrigation followed by 40% , and 15% marginal farmers were using canal and tub well /pump set as a source of irrigation. In case of medium farmers 60% were using own tub well /pump set as a source of irrigation followed by 13% and 27% medium farmers were using canal +private tub well /pump set and canal as a source of irrigation.

Table-9 : Source of irrigation.

S.N.	Source of irr.	Marginal farmers	Small farmers	Medium farmers	Total farmers
1	Own tubwell/pumpset	15	35	60	31
2	Canal	40	44	27	54
3	Canal+private canal pumpset	45	21	13	45

Source: field survey 2016-17

Conclusion : It is a clear from the above analysis that the most of the sugarcane growers belonged to backward caste, medium farmers. 5 to 8 members in a family, belonged to medium income group. In the case of production level most of the farmers belonged to the medium productivity level. Farmers are educated mostly up to 10th class. Majority of the farmers according in all categories belong to joint family. The finding of this study will help the increase and redesign the activities for the technologies in sugarcane crop on the , productivity , marketing and socio-economic status of sugarcane growers.

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